

D7.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

Summary sheet

Project name	SOLAR Photovoltaic to MOVE for Systems Integration
Project acronym	SOLAR-MOVE
Deliverable number	D7.1
Deliverable title	Dissemination and Communication Plan
Deliverable version	Version 2.0
Work Package number	WP7
Work Package title	Dissemination and Standardisation
Due date of delivery	30/04/2026
Actual date of delivery	11/05/2026
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Document/report
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Project starting date	01 November 2025
Project duration	42 Months

Change history

Version	Date	Name/Organisation	Description
0.1	02/03/2026	Mark Meyer (POLIS) Daniel Herrera (POLIS)	Table of contents
0.2	02/04/2026	Mark Meyer (POLIS) Daniel Herrera (POLIS) Vittoria Maddalena (POLIS)	Draft for review and inputs from INESC
0.4	07/04/2026	Daniela Cristina Melo Magalhães (INESC ID) Mariana Carmo (INESC ID)	Contributions
0.5	15/04/2026	Dimitra Tsakanika (DAEM) Iliia Christantoni (DAEM) Nikos Vourgidis (NTUA)	Review of the document
0.6	24/04/2026	Mark Meyer (POLIS) Daniel Herrera (POLIS)	Draft for final review by coordinator
1.0	30/04/2026	Daniela Cristina Melo Magalhães (INESC-ID)	Final version submitted
2.0	11/05/2026	Daniela Cristina Melo Magalhães (INESC-ID) Mark Meyer (POLIS)	Version updated with the PO's requested changes and resubmitted

Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the SOLAR-MOVE project, co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101235635. The views represented in this document only reflect the views of the authors and not the views of the European Commission. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ePIPV	Electric Vehicle Compliant Parking Lot Integrated PV
ER	Expected Result
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
IPV	Integrated Photovoltaics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSO	Key Strategic Orientation
M	Month
MoM	Minutes of Meeting
TG	Target Group
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VIPV	Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaic
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable, D7.1 ‘Dissemination and Communication Plan’ provides the details of the SOLAR-MOVE communication and dissemination activities, including developing strategies to boost visibility through targeted messaging, creating useful communication materials, creating effective communication channels, and supporting and participating in knowledge transfer through publications, events, and interactions with similar initiatives and projects. Detailed information is provided on the brand and style guidelines, printed communication materials created for the project tools, digital communication platforms and resource, as well as information on the KPIs and monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities.

Keywords

Electric vehicles | ePIPv | VIPv | IPV | Strategy | Vehicle-to-grid | Planning | Regulatory | Demonstrations | Replicability | Policy | Communication | Dissemination

1. Introduction

The SOLAR-MOVE project officially started in November 2025 [M1] and will run for 42 months through April 2029 [M42]. This document, D7.1, is the initial Communication and Dissemination (D&C) plan and outlines the communication planning for the lifecycle of the project, derived from the material in the Grant Agreement (GA), as well as discussions since the project started. This document can serve as a guidebook on the brand and style guidelines for partners to use when communicating and submitting official documents, presents the KPIs and further details on the various platforms and materials, and provides information on the printed and digital communication tools created for the project.

The plan will be updated in D7.2, halfway through the project [M24], to address any changes as the project evolves and to update the plan as needed through the end of the project.

1.1 About SOLAR-MOVE

The project overview that follows is extracted from the Grant Agreement (GA) and the project page on the POLIS website. The information contained in the GA is also extracted throughout the document as a reference to the planning and activities to take place within the project.

The SOLAR-MOVE project aims to support the widespread adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) by exploring the potential of Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaic (VIPV) solutions. It will focus on tailored solutions in various types of vehicles to extend their range and reduce dependence on power grids.

The project will have several demonstrations of VIPV systems that address the majority of road transportation usage in cities, residential and service buildings, passenger transportation, and on highways. SOLAR-MOVE will also implement five types of Electric Vehicle Compliant Parking Lot Integrated PV (ePIPv), charging stations with photovoltaic panels.

Pilot projects will be conducted in seven countries:

- Denmark: heavy-duty vehicles and an ePIPv parking lot for trucks
- Greece: VIPV garbage truck and municipal ePIPv management
- Türkiye: VIPV passenger bus and ePIPv bus opportunity charging
- Portugal/New Zealand: last-mile delivery VIPV and public ePIPv management
- Albania: private ePIPv management
- Slovenia: VIPV motorhome

The consortium includes 35 partners in 16 countries. The project findings will contribute to policy recommendations, guidelines for municipalities on procurement processes, and regulatory frameworks to support the widespread adoption of VIPV and ePIPv technologies [1,2].

1.2 SOLAR-MOVE communication overview and objectives

The SOLAR-MOVE project agreement contains an array of wider expected impact, including Key Strategic Orientations (KSOs), Expected Results (ERs), Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which are outlined here and throughout the document.

Overall, the project's ambitions support accelerating and steering green and digital transitions through innovation. On the societal level, the proposed solutions, results of the demonstrations, guidelines, and recommendations will serve as a benchmark to guide the implementation of these technologies in real-world contexts. This supports the wider goals of contributing to the EU's strategic vision to accelerate the green transition by placing these technologies as a focal point of the potential ways forward in this green energy transition.

2. Scope of the communications work package

The communications work package (WP) covers the overall scope of the project's communication and dissemination activities, including developing strategies to boost visibility through targeted messaging, creating useful communication materials, effective communication channels, and supporting and participating in knowledge transfer through publications, events, and interactions with similar initiatives and projects. Further elements of the WP not related to this deliverable/communication and dissemination strategy are only included here as they relate to that focus.

2.1 Deliverable and related tasks

The formal Deliverable and Tasks behind the communication and dissemination (C&D) planning include Tasks 7.1 and 7.2. Success is measured by the achievement of the goals, impacts, and KPIs set out in the Grant Agreement (GA). The following is extracted from the GA:

Work package 7 (WP7) – Dissemination and Standardisation

WP7 aims to disseminate the project's results. The objectives are directly tied to the Tasks and include:

- To develop communication and dissemination strategies to boost the project's visibility through targeted key messages and effective communication channels
- To plan interactions and knowledge transfer by fostering connections with other projects and both national and European initiatives
- To participate and contribute to standardisation bodies
- To publish policy recommendations and guidelines about the adoption of VIPVs and ePIPVs

For this deliverable, the first two bullet points are the primary considerations, and are related to the first two tasks, T7.1 and T7.2.

T7.1 – Communication and Dissemination strategies

This task involves identifying, planning, and executing all C&D activities related to the SOLAR-MOVE project. This strategy, presented here, serves as a guiding document for project partners, detailing target audiences, dissemination channels, KPIs, and partners' roles.

To ensure the outcomes of SOLAR-MOVE effectively reach stakeholders, the plan includes KPIs on research articles, conference participation, social media and website activity, conducting webinars and workshops, contributing to standardisation initiatives, and jointly organising clarification sessions on the pilot/local level on flexibility and bidirectional charging to improve users' literacy on the topics and engagement with SOLAR-MOVE solutions.

T7.2 – Interaction with other projects and initiatives

This task is focused on identifying and establishing collaborative activities with similar projects - including projects addressing the VIPV supply chain, funding opportunities, and initiatives on European, national, and regional levels.

One key initiative outlined in advance is meaningful engagement and participation in the EU’s [BRIDGE](#) initiative and the related meetings, workshops, and Working Groups (e.g., Data Management, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement, and Business Models). SOLAR-MOVE will also participate in events aimed at fostering connections and synergies with other European projects (e.g. [AHEAD](#)). Moreover, the project is going to be part of the V2X CLUSTER, a collaboration initiative among Horizon Europe projects focused on smart charging and V2X (vehicle-to-everything) technologies, to foster knowledge exchange, align approaches and enhance the impact of project results. Also, a collaboration has been established with the sister project, Solar Urban e-Mobility Transition, through initial meetings and exchanges aimed at identifying potential synergies.

All consortium partners will be involved in various aspects, focusing on their strengths. For example, academic and R&D partners will be more active in disseminating project results through scientific articles, attending scientific conferences, and participating in activities with other projects. Industry partners will be more engaged in participating in webinars, attending fairs, and networking events.

The following figure (**Figure 1**) outlines and visualises some of the main dissemination activities of the project:

Figure 1 - Main Dissemination activities of the SOLAR-MOVE project
(Source: GA)

2.2 Communications approach

To maximise the impact of C&D activities, the following overall ‘goals’ should be considered to guide the process of engagement with stakeholders. These are outlined in the GA:

- Raise awareness of the project’s vision and objectives
- Disseminate the research, scientific and technological knowledge generated in SOLAR-MOVE, including SOLAR-MOVE innovations, and inform target groups about their benefits
- Maximise the transfer of knowledge and innovations
- Explore the appropriate market segment to support the exploitation strategy
- Inform regulators and propose regulatory changes
- Foster collaboration and synergy with other projects and initiatives

The primary communication activities are outlined below in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 - Main Communication activities of the SOLAR-MOVE project
(Source: GA)

2.3 Key stakeholders

The SOLAR-MOVE C&D strategy engages different key stakeholder groups with SOLAR-MOVE project content through the project partners and the pilots’ networks, partnerships, projects, fora, associations, and other networks and platforms of which they are members. To multiply the effects of dissemination, all project partners are committed throughout the project to mobilise the relevant stakeholders through their networking profiles.

The stakeholders identified for the project were broken down into the following Target Groups (TGs), ‘end-users’ and ‘stakeholder ecosystem’. The details are available in **Table 1**. C&D activities geared towards TG1-TG7, end-users, will be tailored to engage and inform current and potential owners/end-users of VIPVs and ePIPVs. C&D activities for TG8-TG14, the wider stakeholder ecosystem, will promote collaboration and support focused on development and adoption, including specific activities

(webinars, workshops, events), and the advisory board. The stakeholder groups play key roles, not only as an audience of the results, but also as a source of insight, diverse perspectives, and input when seeking to advance the proposed solutions, innovations, and regulations. Engagement with stakeholders supports alignment with market expectations.

Table 1 - SOLAR-MOVE Target Groups (TGs)
(Source: GA)

Target Groups	Description
End Users	TG1 EV drivers/owners and families, vehicle operators.
	TG2 Garbage Trucks + Commercial fleet managers.
	TG3 Bus fleet managers.
	TG4 Post company (transportation) and distribution fleet managers.
	TG5 Retailers (e.g. SONAE).
	TG6 Last-Mile delivery fleet managers.
	TG7 Motorhome drivers/travellers and fleet managers.
Stakeholder ecosystem	TG8 PV cell manufactures and PV integrators.
	TG9 Vehicle manufactures; Fleet operators; Battery manufactures, OEMs, and electronic equipment manufactures.
	TG10 Energy industry: System operators (DSO, TSO), energy producers, energy retailers and aggregators, energy service companies, VPP, and CPO.
	TG11 Research and Academia: Scientific Community, R&D, Students, Programme projects/joint actions, and European open science cloud.
	TG12 Technology providers: software companies, hardware devise, IoT services, building operators, weather services, and cybersecurity solutions.
	TG13 Standardisation Bodies: BRIDGE, IEC, CIRED, ISO, and IEA.
	TG14 Policymakers, Public Authorities and Regulators: EU commission, European parliament, city mayors, and members states heads.

3. Brand and style guidelines

The SOLAR-MOVE project established, defined, and adopted a branding identity and related visual identifiers by month 4 (M4) of the project. This was prioritised so that the project can benefit from clear visibility of the project and objectives, and association of the SOLAR-MOVE project with vehicle and infrastructure photovoltaic technologies, etc. from the early stages.

A SOLAR-MOVE brand identity handbook was developed by M6, and provides guidelines and suggestions about the usage and application of the corporate design, project logo, and acknowledgement to EU funding. This document is available on the consortium's shared drive for project colleagues and will also be published on the project website.

The guidelines for the project's visual identity include information on, e.g.:

- The SOLAR-MOVE logo, which must appear on every project-related item (documents, banners, videos, giveaways, etc.).
- The EU funding acknowledgement, logo characteristics, project official colours, font policy, image policy, and references to digital tools.

Further details on EU funding acknowledgement and flag usage can be found in **Appendix A**.

Partners can find the complete information on the collective drive. The following figures (**Figure 3-10**) outline some of the key components/guidelines of the brand guidelines:

Title

The project title must be written in upper case (capital letters) as 'SOLAR-MOVE', with a hyphen separating 'SOLAR' and 'MOVE' and without any spaces between the words.

SOLAR-MOVE ✓

SOLARMOVE ✗

SOLAR MOVE ✗

Funding acknowledgement

SOLAR-MOVE is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101235635.

EU Emblem

The EU emblem below must accompany the funding acknowledgement.

Figure 3 - SOLAR-MOVE project title and funding statement

Isotype

The SOLAR-MOVE isotype combines symbolic elements that represent the core concept of the project: solar-powered mobility. The circular icon evokes the shape of a vehicle wheel, directly referencing movement and transportation. The upper yellow arc represents the sun and solar energy, while the blue segmented shapes symbolize solar panels. Together, these elements visually communicate the integration of renewable energy with mobility solutions, reflecting the project's commitment to sustainable and innovative transport systems.

Colours

SOLAR-MOVE's colour palette is built around two main colours: yellow and blue. The yellow represents the sun and the generation of clean solar energy, conveying brightness, sustainability, and environmental responsibility. The blue represents solar panels and technology, symbolizing reliability, innovation, and energy conversion. The contrast between these colours highlights the relationship between sunlight and solar energy capture, reinforcing the project's focus on renewable energy applied to mobility.

Logotype

The logotype uses a bold, modern sans-serif typeface that conveys strength, innovation, and technological progress. The name SOLAR-MOVE is written in uppercase letters with a hyphen separating the two words, reinforcing clarity and readability. The typographic style reflects the project's focus on modern mobility solutions powered by renewable energy, while maintaining a clean and contemporary visual identity suitable for scientific, technological, and environmental contexts.

Figure 4 - SOLAR-MOVE logo

Horizontal logo

Vertical logo

Centre logo

Figure 5 - SOLAR-MOVE logo variations

Figure 6 - Logos on backgrounds

Figure 7 - Improper use of logos

Figure 8 - SOLAR-MOVE colour scheme

Calibri Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
~ ! @ # \$ % & / | \ () []

Heading 1: Calibri 16pt Bold - Blue

Heading 2: Calibri 14pt Bold - Black

Heading 3: Calibri 12pt Bold - Blue

Heading 4: Calibri 11pt Bold - Black

All template sections and body text: 11 pt

Calibri Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
~ ! @ # \$ % & / | \ () []

Figure 9 - Typography and fonts

Partners should use the styles, fonts, and font sizes defined in the templates. EU project guidelines require the use of standard **British English**. The deliverable text must be justified. When sections or chapters are mentioned in the text, a cross-reference to the corresponding section or chapter should be included.

Font: Calibri

Font sizes (heading sizes are pre-defined - please do not modify them):

Other text sizes:

- 'Normal': All template sections and body text: 11 pt. (Hex: #272626)
- Text within figures and tables: 11 pt.
- Figure and table captions: 11 pt.

For Word documents / Deliverables text should be justified (except tables).

Figures and tables should have captions and be centred. If a citation is needed, sources can be listed on a second line so that this additional information does not take up space in the List of Figures or List of Tables. The space between these lines can be removed.

Figure 10 - References to website and social media

Images used for the project in news, social media, etc., should represent vehicles, infrastructure, colleagues, and themes directly related to the project. These images should be cited appropriately, e.g.: *The photos and images used in 'document title' have been created by project partners (and/or cited appropriately).

The official language for all materials is British English. The coordination and communications teams can support the creation of localised/translated materials if the project coordinator agrees that this would be a more effective approach for certain local activities.

To complement the visual identity, digital templates for the harmonisation of documents have been made available. These include a Word template for Deliverables, a PowerPoint presentation template, a Word Minutes of Meeting (MoM) template, and an agenda template. SOLAR-MOVE partners should adhere to the provided design handbook, along with the information provided here, and use these as a guide when creating C&D materials, Deliverables, etc.

4. Printed communication tools (non-digital)

Printed communication tools support a physical presence of the project at official events and other in-person activities. These support increased visibility and, in the case of flyers and business cards, provide something for participants to take with them as a resource that can be used later to find project platforms and information.

4.1 Roll-up (banner)

The roll-up serves to enhance visibility (and wayfinding) of the project at events, general assemblies, and other such events. It is envisioned that two of these will be printed to ease sharing between partners and activities. The roll-ups can be transported, and once set up, create a very large physical advertisement which highlights the overall themes, partners, goals, and primary communication channels of the project. **Figure 11** presents the roll-up banner developed for this project.

Figure 11 - SOLAR-MOVE roll-up

4.2 Brochure and business cards

In addition to the roll-up, two brochures/factsheets will be produced for the project. This provides a bit further detail on the project than the roll-ups and serves as display material for event exhibition areas, consortium organisation offices, etc., to bring further visibility and provide a portable project reference.

The first of these was recently created. Two versions of this project brochure will be made available: an online version and a print version. To minimise waste, printing can be done on demand / as needed by project partners. Both versions will be available for download on the project website. A preview of the brochure is in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12 - SOLAR-MOVE brochure preview

The second brochure (KPI: 2) has been produced in the format of a business card (**Figure 13**), rather than the traditional larger format. As projects evolve away from printed materials, to be more sustainable, a business card was created to provide a much smaller and more portable resource to connect people to the project. This includes the visual identity, a very brief overview, and a QR code linking to the project website. The website efficiently enables stakeholders to sign up for the project newsletter and connect to social media channels.

Figure 13 - SOLAR-MOVE business card

5. Digital communication tools

Digital communication tools provide the key elements of day-to-day communication and dissemination. Partners can create presentations and provide key documents, such as Deliverables by using templates that identify the project and streamline the process. The website serves as a core platform for providing information about the project, publishing documents, and sharing news. Social media supports visibility and gaining 'followers'/and audience for project activities. Newsletters provide regular updates. Workshops and webinars provide opportunities for fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing.

5.1 Templates

Templates were created for Deliverables (Microsoft Word) and presentations (PowerPoint). The templates aim to provide more than just a superficial design. Functionality was added to support everyday usage in the project. Margins and logos were minimised to maximise the space for content. Features and settings were integrated into the templates to streamline the process of partners providing and sharing content and results. This includes the page margins, cover page, table of contents, fonts, spacing, header styles, table settings, integrated colours, footer details, etc. Templates for Minutes of Meeting (MoM) and meeting agendas (e.g. agenda for the General Assembly and Webinars) have also been created.

5.2 Website

The project website serves as the main information channel for the project. The website provides an overview of the project, partners, details of the pilots, and activities, including news, updates, and events. It also efficiently directs stakeholders to sign up for the newsletter and follow social media channels. It serves as a repository for project resources, such as informational/printable materials, and project outputs / Deliverables. Overall, the aim is for the website to be a comprehensive source of project information, to increase awareness and engagement. The project website can be found at: <https://solar-move.eu/>. **Figure 14** presents the homepage of the project website.

Figure 14 - SOLAR-MOVE website

The website is designed to be straightforward and user-friendly. The visual aspect is aligned with the project's identity.

It is structured around five pages, highlighting different aspects of the project:

- The 'About' page is dedicated to introducing the project's scope and key facts, providing an overview of its objectives and approach.
- The 'Partners' page introduces one by one the different consortium partners, providing key information such as the name, logo, website, and social media accounts.
- The 'Pilots' page provides an overview of the ten demonstrations of the project, divided according to the solution type (VIPV or eIPV), and to the country where they are taking place. Each section includes a brief explanation of the pilot, highlighting the main features, objectives, and involved partners.
- The 'Resources' page will serve as the main depository for the project's Deliverables, scientific publications and promotional materials.
- The 'News & Events' page serves as the main channel for updates on the project and partners, as well as events that can be relevant for the audience.
 - The sub-page 'Newsletter' will contain online versions of each public newsletter.
- The 'Contact us' page contains the contact information and a contact form.

In addition, recurring elements throughout the different pages include the invitation to sign up to the newsletter as well as the social media channels.

5.3 Social media

The social media communication strategy aims to reach a broad range of stakeholders and further promote the project. A consistent presence increases website traffic and visibility, and complements established communication channels, such as the website, newsletters, and live events.

The posts on social media channels feature project updates and milestones. The visuals, videos, and photos posted aim to be in line with the project's identity, ensuring that it is coherent and recognisable. Finer details of the social media KPIs are outlined in **Appendix B**.

In addition, throughout the duration of the project, several *ad-hoc* social media campaigns will be implemented. These aim to further increase engagement and promote continued growth throughout the lifecycle of the project. Examples of social media campaigns include introducing the consortium partners, explaining the project's key concepts, and showcasing the pilots.

When publishing original posts, the following hashtags can be featured:

#SOLARMOVE

#Emobility

#SolarPower

#EVs

#Photovoltaic

LinkedIn

SOLAR-MOVE's LinkedIn page is run by POLIS. The social media platform is targeted towards professionals and transport and energy experts, favouring engagement with key stakeholders. The LinkedIn account was created in M2 of the project, and midway through M6, it already has 119 followers. The POLIS team, in collaboration with the project's partners, will update the page and post about project updates, as well as initiatives, events, other projects, and news with synergies that may be relevant to the target audience. The platform's strategy features various formats besides original posts, including reposts and links to other synergies/relevant activity.

The project's LinkedIn page was started in the first months of the project and can be found here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/solar-move/>. **Figure 15** shows the LinkedIn header of the project and **Figure 16** the first post which was about the Kick-off project meeting held in Brussels on the 21st of November.

Figure 15 - LinkedIn header

SOLAR-MOVE

105 followers

1mo • 🌐

SOLAR-MOVE has officially kicked-off! 🇪🇺

SOLAR-MOVE is a new Horizon Europe project exploring how integrated ...more

Figure 16 - SOLAR-MOVE LinkedIn

Instagram

The Instagram account of SOLAR-MOVE aims to increase the effectiveness of dissemination and exploitation activities and to reach a large audience to encourage interaction with key stakeholders. The Instagram account was created in M5 of the project. The posts shared on the platform predominantly aim to share project updates, milestones, events, partners' updates, and other relevant news.

The strategy for Instagram features various formats, including Instagram stories, reposts, and reels, besides feed posts. **Figure 17** shows the Instagram profile page. The account can be found under the handle '@solarmove_project' on Instagram and https://www.instagram.com/solarmove_project/

Figure 17 - SOLAR-MOVE Instagram

5.4 Press releases and newsletters

Press releases serve to broadly disseminate project milestones, with the aim of catching stakeholder attention through more traditional and localised channels.

The first press release was published in February 2026, sent via AlphaGalileo, a media service that supports the distribution of such materials (academic, science, etc.) through a subscription model. An additional press release was adapted for the Portuguese media and distributed by INESC ID. These combined efforts secured 13 articles across various media outlets. The first part of the press release is presented in **Figure 18**.

The SOLAR-MOVE project aims to support the widespread adoption of EVs by exploring the potential of integrated photovoltaic solutions.

25/02/2026 [POLIS AISBL](#)

Led by INESC ID, the Horizon Project will develop customised solutions for different types of solar-powered vehicles and infrastructures.

[Lisbon, February 2026] – The Horizon SOLAR-MOVE project, coordinated by Portuguese R&D Institute [INESC-ID](#), kicked off in November 2025 at [POLIS](#) headquarters in Belgium, one of the consortium partners. The project will run for 42 months, concluding in April 2029, with a maximum grant amount of approximately 7 million Euros. The consortium will count on the expertise of 34 partners across 16 countries.

As road transport becomes electrified, it puts additional pressure on power grids. To address this challenge and facilitate the adoption of EVs, the SOLAR-MOVE project aims to develop and test Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaic (VIPV) solutions. These solutions will target the main areas of road transport, including cities, residential and service buildings, passenger transport, and highways. Demonstrations will include five types of VIPVs:

- Heavy-Duty vehicles with solar panels on trailers;
- Garbage trucks;
- Passenger buses;
- Last-Mile delivery vehicles;
- Motorhomes.

Figure 18 - Press release #1

Newsletters serve to provide periodic updates of the project. These contain updates covering recent activity and accomplishments within the various work packages of the project, highlight upcoming activity and events, and serve as a resource to point stakeholders towards more detailed outputs and full deliverables. The newsletter template is in the final stages of preparation. The KPI is set at 14 newsletters to be produced during the project. Below (**Figure 19**) is an example of the banner on the project website, inviting visitors to sign up for the newsletter. Further details and KPIs/timing of the newsletters are available in **Appendix B**.

Figure 19 - Newsletter sign up – website

5.5 Videos

A project video will be produced to increase awareness and showcase the project in different ways than printed/online materials. These have the potential to provide an efficient visual and audio overview of the project and real video examples of the demos, bringing the perception of the activities closer to reality for stakeholders and potential end users. Further details will be discussed once the pilots are active/well-established.

5.6 Online webinars and workshops

Three workshops will be organised. These will be co-designed with internal partners and involve external initiatives. These will address usability and aesthetic factors in VIPV solutions. The primary target groups are TG1-TG7 (see **Table 1**). In relation to standardisation, there are also plans on the exploitation level, organised with business actors, to promote VIPV and ePIPV solutions developed within SOLAR-MOVE. Project colleagues also plan to contribute to BRIDGE workshops and will be open to participating in other workshops the project aligns with and is invited to.

Five webinars will be organised to raise awareness of VIPVs, ePIPVs and SOLAR-MOVE solutions. These will be public and aim to be of interest to all levels of stakeholders/target groups. The themes of these webinars will develop naturally over time and in discussions as the project evolves.

Overlapping with these activities are liaisons and joint activities with other projects, communities, and initiatives, which can take place within these webinars and workshops, as well as other activities such as joint publications. The goal is to gather ideas, knowledge, and exchange best practices with similar initiatives.

6. Events

Participation in events and interaction with other projects and initiatives will play a key role in the project. Much of this is covered in T7.2 of the project, Interaction with other projects and initiatives. This was covered in the overview of the WP and tasks. In direct relation to events, the aim is to identify and establish collaborative relationships to support connections and synergies with similar European initiatives and projects, including the **EU's BRIDGE** initiative and the **AHEAD project**, as well as the **V2X Cluster** and the **SOLAR Urban e-Mobility Transition project** (the sister project of SOLAR-MOVE). In addition, in line with the objectives of Task 7.2, SOLAR-MOVE will actively pursue strategic clustering and knowledge-exchange activities with relevant sister and complementary projects in the fields of vehicle-integrated photovoltaics (VIPV), integrated photovoltaics (IPV), smart charging and zero-emission road transport. These synergies may include bilateral exchanges, joint webinars, common thematic sessions and coordinated participation in major European conferences and stakeholder events, with the objective of amplifying the visibility, transferability and policy relevance of SOLAR-MOVE results. SOLAR-MOVE will also seek to position its dissemination and communication activities in alignment with broader European initiatives and platforms, such as the [2ZERO partnership](#) and [ETIP PV](#), in order to contribute to ongoing discussions on innovation uptake, interoperability and standardisation pathways for solar-integrated mobility solutions. SOLAR-MOVE will also take part in outreach events, such as participation in European Research Night, to enhance end-users' awareness.

SOLAR-MOVE partners will also interact with the general public and other experts through talks, conferences, and initiatives which support public engagement and promote the European Commission's mission of **100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030**.

Project partners will list potentially relevant conferences and events which attract stakeholders, and document their level of participation so project colleagues are all aware. These events allow dissemination and exchange, and networking.

The following represents a preliminary list of relevant EU and national events for promotion. This list will be updated and extended throughout the duration of the project:

- TRA Conference
- RTR Conference
- Annual POLIS Conference
- European Transport Conference
- ITS Congress Europe
- EVS Congress
- ENLIT Europe
- IEEE PES Conference

7. Publications

The main objective of the SOLAR-MOVE project is to propose, develop, and demonstrate viable VIPV and eIPV solutions. In line with the priorities of the European Commission (EC), the SOLAR-MOVE consortium will adopt an Open Science strategy. This Open Science strategy includes publishing scientific articles in peer-reviewed Open Access scientific journals, for the findings to be available to all researchers and public in general.

Articles will be published by partners in specialised magazines (KPI: 2) to share detailed knowledge, improvements and solutions. Scientific publications (KPI: 25) will be submitted to share detailed knowledge created in the project, which allows other researchers and future projects to build upon the findings of SOLAR-MOVE.

It is planned to have joint publications with similar initiatives and projects to gather ideas and exchange knowledge and best practices.

Additionally, towards the conclusion of the project, guidelines will be provided to promote VIPV and eIPV adoption, support the project's long-term impact, and avoid wasted time from overlapping research by sharing progress with projects just beginning and in the future.

The GA outlines tools, platforms, and the approach to sharing information for the project. Some of the key information extracted from the GA includes the following information:

- The SOLAR-MOVE partners intend to share project research outputs, tools, and instruments, to allow others to access, use, and develop. To this end, SOLAR-MOVE partners plan to adopt free and open-source software licenses...and share the outputs in dedicated trusted repositories (e.g., GitHub).
- SOLAR-MOVE will provide open access to published scientific articles and results through trusted European Commission repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Open Research Europe platform, and EIRIE platform).
- Whenever significant data or research outputs are highlighted, they will be published on open repositories, such as Zenodo, to allow partners and interested third parties to consult them. They will remain accessible after the end of SOLAR-MOVE.' (GA)

Partners will be reminded to include in all publications, including scientific articles, the following disclaimer (under the acknowledgement section):

“This work received co-funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101235635. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

8. Monitoring of C&D activities

To evaluate the impact of the project's dissemination activities, the SOLAR-MOVE consortium established, during proposal preparation and Grant Agreement (GA), a specific set of metrics to effectively monitor its achievements. The KPIs are presented in the tables below in section 8.1. These KPIs will be monitored monthly throughout the project to evaluate progress in communication and dissemination (C&D) activities and inform interim and annual reports.

8.1 Key Performance Indicators

The following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are designed to measure both the reach (quantity) and the engagement (quality) of the project's activities. These metrics enable the consortium to conduct impact assessments for reporting and allow the coordination and communication team to adapt and adjust the strategy to align with the present context and optimise outreach as the project evolves.

Table 2 below provides the quantitative framework for the project's communication channels, tools and materials, setting measurable targets for digital presence, participation in outreach events, and publication output to ensure high visibility throughout the 42-month period.

Table 3 below includes the goals for dissemination activities such as workshops, events, and publications and outlines the quantitative targets agreed in the GA.

During the development of the C&D plan, the initial KPIs were refined to better align with project goals. The new KPIs were defined to ensure a balanced approach, addressing both technical aspects targeted at experts and more general indicators aimed at a broader audience. The final targets, presented in the tables below, already reflect this strategic shift promoting high-quality engagement. The initial proposed numbers and clarification of changes can be found in **Table B 1, Appendix B**.

Table 2 - Communication tools, channels, and KPIs / Final targets 2026

(Source: GA)

Channel	KPI	Targets	Status: M6	Expected Impact	TG's
SOLAR-MOVE Website	No. of unique visitors	2 000	N/A	Main online information channel; Liaisons with other initiatives, projects, and WG; Communication of project news, events, and outcomes; Increase awareness and engagement with the project	All TGs
	Average duration of visits	1 min	N/A		
	No. of page views	5 000	N/A		
	Deliverable downloads	300	N/A		
Project LinkedIn	No. of accumulative followers	500	120	Increased visibility and interest of TGs and citizens; Direct communication with followers, engagement with the project	All TGs
	No. of posts (Including posts and re-posts)	144	3 posts + 4 reposts		
Project second social media (Instagram)	No. of accumulative followers	200	22		
	No. of posts	72	1		
Publications in general media	No. of articles in magazines, newspapers	20	13	Increased project visibility and impact on society	All TGs
Outreach events	Participation in events such as European Research Night	3	0	Enhance end users' awareness of EU projects and VIPVs and ePIPVs	TG1-TG7
Branding and communication kit	No. of press releases	2	1	Communication of project news, events, and results; Increased awareness; Unique branding and visual identity of the project	All TGs
	Factsheets / brochures	2	2		
	presentations	1	1		
	posters	4	0		
	banners	1	1		
	eNewsletters	14: 7 external, 7 internal	0		
videos	1	0			

Table 3 - Dissemination activity aims / Final targets 2026

(Source: GA)

KPI	Target	Status: M6	Dissemination activities aim	Target Groups (TGs)	Tools and channels
No. of workshops organised	3	0	Co-design workshop addressing usability and aesthetic factors in VIPV solutions	TG1-TG7	Project presentation, poster brochure, leaflets
No. of attendees to the project workshops	40	0			
Clarification sessions	5	0	Enhancing end users' awareness and understanding of SOLAR-MOVE solutions	TG1-TG7	Project presentation, brochures, leaflets
No. of demo events	4	0	Dissemination of results to target groups, identification of cooperation opportunities, and increased awareness and engagement of end users	All	Project presentation, brochure, leaflets, social media, media news, website
Webinars	5	0	Increase awareness on VIPVs and ePIPVs and SOLAR-MOVE solutions and external monitorisation of the project, organised every 6 months, starting M9	All	Brochure, leaflets, poster, roll-up, website
Attendance in events	20	2	Dissemination and exchange during conferences, networking events, and industry fairs attracting energy system stakeholders	TG8-TG14	Brochure, leaflets, Project presentation, roll-up, poster
No. of events where the project has been presented	5	0			
No. of articles in specialised magazines	2	0	Share the detailed knowledge created in the project to allow industry to improve and create new solutions, and policymakers to follow	TG8 TG9 TG10 TG12	Industry press, media, conferences
No. of scientific publications	25	1	Share the detailed knowledge created in the project to allow other researchers to build upon the findings of the project	TG10, TG11 TG12	Conferences, scientific press, media

8.3 Policy recommendations

As outlined in the GA and evident from the rapid advances in innovation, technology, and the market for VIPV and the installation of ePIPV, there is often a lack of clear policies and incentives to support the adoption of VIPV and the installation of ePIPV.

There are regulatory gaps in integrating VIPVs and ePIPVs into grid infrastructure and V2G systems.

There are also inconsistencies in policy across member states and the various levels of governance, and room for improvement in the balance of input and cooperation between government and industry. To help mitigate this, the project plans to organise webinars and exchanges with policymakers (governments and municipalities).

There are unclear/insufficient liability frameworks established in many areas of VIPVs, and the safety and interoperability of ePIPV systems.

To address these, SOLAR-MOVE will propose a strategic positioning framework and publish policy recommendations.

8.4 Opportunities - making use of the consortium's network

The project covers a wide array of pilot activities, vehicles and partners, with 35 partners in 16 countries, representing a significant opportunity to maximise the impact of C&D activities. The project aims to contribute to policy recommendations, procurement processes, and regulatory frameworks supporting the adoption of VIPV and ePIPV technology.

All organisations that are part of the project are expected to contribute to C&D activities, with a focus on their area of expertise and tasks within the project. This includes a range of potential options such as attending relevant events and showcasing their efforts, producing publications, organising and participating in workshops with similar initiatives and projects, and social media posts/activity. Ideally, partners utilise their own networks via their own communication channels, such as websites, newsletters, and social media, to expand the reach of the project activities and results.

Some of the specific activities related to the local pilots include the clarification sessions to enhance end users' awareness and understanding of SOLAR-MOVE solutions. These should aim to cover flexibility and bidirectional charging to improve end-users' energy literacy and engagement with SOLAR-MOVE solutions. There will also be four demo events to disseminate the results, identify opportunities to cooperate, and increase awareness and engagement. Posters should be created for these activities and, when relevant, for conferences. These and other materials can be localised if deemed necessary or more effective, as mentioned in the branding chapter.

These activities expand the project's outreach and contribute to achieving the project's C&D KPIs. Active engagement of the consortium's network provides a key contribution to enhancing the visibility and impact of project results.

9. Conclusion

This Deliverable, D7.1 ‘Dissemination and Communication Plan’ provided the details of the SOLAR-MOVE communication and dissemination activities, including developing strategies to boost visibility through targeted messaging, creating useful communication materials, creating effective communication channels, and supporting and participating in knowledge transfer through publications, events, and interactions with similar initiatives and projects. Detailed information was provided on the brand and style guidelines, printed communication materials created for the project tools, digital communication platforms and resources, as well as information on the KPIs and monitoring of the C&D activities.

The plan will be updated in D7.2, halfway through the project [M24], to address any changes as the project evolves and to update the plan as needed through the end of the project.

The key tables from this document have also been placed in **Appendix B**, which serves as a consolidated overview of the finer details of the communication channels, KPIs, stakeholders, etc.

10. References

- [1] European Commission. (2025). SOLAR-MOVE Grant Agreement No. 101235635. European Commission, Funding & Tenders Portal.
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Appendix A: EU funding acknowledgement and flag usage

The European Commission provides a download centre for visual elements [3].

Title of the most commonly used flag for this project: EN_Co-fundedbytheEU_RGB_POS

Figure A 1 - Co-funded by the European Union

The following extracts key details and visuals from a document provided by the European Commission providing information on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes, 'Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding' [4]. This guidance should be followed when these elements are included in project materials.

Positive version
(CMYK or digital impression process)

Negative version

Figure A 2 - EU Flag positive and negative versions

Protection area

The protection area must remain free of competing texts, logos, images or any other visual element that could compromise its good legibility.

Minimum size

The minimum height of the EU emblem must be 1 cm.

For specific items, like pens, the emblem can be reproduced in a smaller size.

When using the EU funding statement in a small size, we highly recommend using the horizontal version.

Figure A 3 - Size and spacing guidelines for EU info

Placement of the EU emblem with the funding statement on communication material

The EU emblem, in conjunction with the funding statement, must be prominently featured on all communication material, such as printed or digital products or websites and their mobile version, intended for the public or for participants.

The placement of the EU emblem should not give the impression that the beneficiary or third party is connected in any way to the EU institutions. It is therefore recommended to place the EU emblem at a distance from the third-party organisation's logo.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

Figure A 4 - Placement of EU funding statement on comms materials

Placement of the EU emblem with the funding statement in case of co-branding

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

The beneficiaries may use the emblem without first having obtained approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trade mark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Figure A 5 - Placement of the EU emblem and funding statement (co-branding)

Don'ts

Do not choose a font other than Arial, Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu or Verdana.

Do not use any font effects.

Do not add other graphic elements.

Do not make the text disproportionately bigger or smaller compared to the EU emblem.

Do not use any colour other than Reflex blue, white or black.

Do not modify the text proportions.

Do not write 'EU'. It must always be spelled out as 'European'.

Do not write in all capital letters.

Do not replace the EU emblem with the European Commission logo.

Do not replace the EU emblem with any other graphic element.

Do not modify the EU emblem.

Do not add the name of the programme to the funding statement.

Do not write the name of the programme in conjunction with the EU emblem.

Do not add a graphical element with the name of the EU programme.

Figure A 6 - Don't - EU emblem and funding statements

Appendix B: KPIs and dissemination monitoring

Table B 1 - Communication tools, channels, and KPIs / Changes justifications

(Source: GA)

Channel	KPI	Original Targets	New Target	Deviation justifications
SOLAR-MOVE Website	Average duration of visits	*2 min	1 min	*Average duration of visits: 1 min. The project will prioritise engagement over volume.
	Deliverable downloads	300	300	Deliverables will be in the Zenodo repository, and downloads are also going to be tracked both on the Website and Zenodo.
Project LinkedIn	No. of posts	*168	144 (posts + reposts)	*Main social media activity starting once the project has been sufficiently established after M6. Goal: ~1 post every two weeks (36Mx2) + reposts (72). Content includes campaigns and coverage of relevant project activity / events.
Project second social media (Instagram)	No. of posts	*168	72	*Instagram posts will start once the project has been sufficiently established after M6. Goal: ~1 post every two weeks (36Mx2). Overall, LinkedIn is seen as the most useful platform to reach stakeholders with detailed information. Instagram posts will more visual and aim to guide potential stakeholders to the project's LinkedIn account, website, and other key content.
Branding and communication kit	eNewsletters	*14, every 3 months	14	14 total: 7 external (newsletters ~every six months) and 7 internal newsletters.